

Title: How Tax and Securities Laws Can Help or Hurt Blockchain Businesses and Investors

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INTRODUCTION:

Blockchain and shared ledger technologies have opened the door to incredible opportunities for businesses to find new efficiencies and for investors to generate new wealth. As a result, the number of businesses and investors in the space has proliferated exponentially in the past 12 months. This has caused government regulators to scramble to adapt tax and securities laws and regulations to the new realities of cross border token offerings and sales of cryptocurrencies which occur in multiple jurisdictions in real-time.

AIM:

To address the tax and securities issues which arise when businesses and individuals raise money from the public to finance Blockchain projects, as well as tax issues which arise when trading in cryptocurrencies.

KEYWORDS:

Cryptocurrency, Blockchain, Distributed Ledger, Initial Coin Offering

BIOGRAPHY:

Aaron Grinhaus is an experienced business and tax consultant who has developed a niche expertise in the use of Fintech strategies, including the use of blockchain technology, smart contracts and cryptocurrency. Mr. Grinhaus is a business and tax lawyer by trade, and his firm (grinhauslaw.ca) was one of the first firms in Canada to publicly advise on the practical uses of blockchain and shared ledger technology, as well as accept cryptocurrencies as payment. Mr. Grinhaus holds law degrees from University of Ottawa (LL.B.), Michigan State University College of Law (J.D.) and a Masters in Tax Law from Osgoode Hall Law School of York University (LL.M.)